

SIDE-CHAIN BROMINATION OF SOME AROMATIC COMPOUNDS WITH *N*-BROMOSUCCINIMIDE

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The side-chain bromination of a number of aromatic compounds with *N*-bromosuccinimide using benzoyl peroxide as a catalyst has been described.

N-Bromosuccinimide is now widely used as a specific reagent for the introduction of a bromine atom in olefins at the allyl or α -methylene position without the simultaneous addition to the double bond (Ziegler *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1942, 551, 80; Djerassi, *Chem. Rev.*, 1948, 43, 271). A homolytic mechanism has been proposed for the reaction.

Small quantities of the peroxide favour the formation of radicals and therefore increase the yield and velocity of bromination with *N*-bromosuccinimide. Through the introduction of this method, many compounds, which were formerly difficult to prepare, have now become easily accessible. It is known that while no 'side-chain' bromination of toluene occurs when this compound is treated with *N*-bromosuccinimide under the original conditions used by Ziegler (cf. Buu-Hoï, *Annalen*, 1944, 556, 1), the introduction of a small quantity of benzoyl peroxide as a catalyst results in the formation of benzyl bromide in good yield (Schmid and Karrer, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1946, 29, 573). In the presence of electronegative groups, two instances have been reported earlier (Buu-Hoï, *loc. cit.* Djerassi, *loc. cit.*) where 'side-chain' bromination occurs even in the absence of a catalyst.

The side-chain bromination of a number of aromatic compounds with *N*-bromosuccinimide, in the presence of benzoyl peroxide as a catalyst, has now been studied. It has been found that the use of the catalyst facilitates the introduction of bromine in the side-chain, increases the yield of the product and the reaction time is reduced appreciably. Also it has been found that the use of an excess of the compound to be brominated leads to better overall yields, as would be observed from the appended table.

Thus, while Buu-Hoï (*loc. cit.*) observed that *p*-nitrobenzyl bromide was formed from *p*-nitrotoluene in 50% yield, with the introduction of peroxide this compound was formed in a yield of 77.5% and the reaction time was reduced to two hours. Similar results have been obtained with the side-chain bromination of *o*-chlorotoluene. This method also results in the formation of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-methylbenzyl bromides from

TABLE I

Compound	Ratio of mols. of compound to mols. of <i>N</i> -bromosuccinimide	Duration of reaction	Bromide obtained	B. p. or m.p.	% Yield	Formula*	S-Alkyl-isothiourea picrate	
							M. p.	Nitrogen % Found. Calc.
<i>o</i> -Xylene	2	2 hrs.	<i>o</i> -Methylbenzyl-*	95-99°/9mm.	86.5	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₅ S	199-200°	17 17.1
<i>m</i> -Xylene	1	2	<i>m</i> -Methylbenzyl-*	98-99°/9mm.	62.2	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₅ S	175-77°	16.7 17.1
<i>p</i> -Xylene	1	3	<i>p</i> -Methylbenzyl-*	98-100°/9mm.	48.6	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₅ S	203-205°	17.4 17.1
	2	2	"	106°/12mm.	69.9	"	"	—
<i>m</i> -Nitrotoluene	2	2	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzyl-	169-71°/8mm.	63.6	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₅ S	188°	18.8 19.1
<i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene	1	2½	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzyl-	95-96°	50.8	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₇ N ₅ S	197°	18.7 19.1
	2	2	"	"	77.5	"	"	—
<i>o</i> -Methoxytoluene	2	2	<i>o</i> -Methoxybenzyl-	134-35°/11mm.	50	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₈ N ₅ S	189-90°	15.5 16.5
<i>o</i> -Chlorotoluene	1	2	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzyl-	110°/10mm.	81	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₅ ClS	210° (213°)	—
	2	2	"	"	84	"	—	—
<i>m</i> -Chlorotoluene	1	2	<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzyl-	96°/6mm.	72.7	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₅ ClS	195° (200°)	—
<i>p</i> -Chlorotoluene	1	3	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzyl-	110-17°/8-10mm.	76.2	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₅ ClS	190° (194°)	—
<i>o</i> -Bromotoluene	2	2	<i>o</i> -Bromobenzyl-	115-17°/11mm.	69.1	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₅ BrS	215° (222°)	—
<i>m</i> -Bromotoluene	2	3	<i>m</i> -Bromobenzyl-	113-14°/10mm.	55.3	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₅ BrS	203° (205°)	—
<i>p</i> -Bromotoluene	2	2	<i>p</i> -Bromobenzyl-	119-21°/6mm. m.p. 61-62°	63.7	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₅ BrS	217° (219°)	—

* A small quantity of the xylyl bromide is also formed.

the corresponding toluenes in good yields. *o*-Nitrobenzyl bromide could not be prepared in this way, as decomposition occurred during distillation of the product, formed from the reaction with *N*-bromosuccinimide.

All the substituted benzyl bromides formed have been identified by the preparation of the *S*-alkyl-isothiourea picrates according to the directions of Levy and Campbell (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1442).

EXPERIMENTAL*

N-Bromosuccinimide was prepared in 75% yield by the bromination of an alkaline solution of succinimide using the method of Ziegler *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). After crystallisation from hot water, it melted at 172.5° (slow) or 177.5° (rapid).

Bromination of p-Xylene.—A mixture of *p*-xylene (10.6 g.), *N*-bromosuccinimide (8.9 g.), benzoyl peroxide (0.25 g.) and dry carbon tetrachloride (50 c.c.) was boiled under reflux in a three-necked flask, fitted with a mechanical stirrer. After the reaction had subsided, more benzoyl peroxide (0.25 g.) was added and heating continued under stirring. The reaction was over in about an hour as no more bromine was noticed to evolve. At the end of two hours, the mixture was cooled and allowed to stand overnight and the precipitated succinimide was filtered off. After removal of the carbon tetrachloride, the residual liquid was fractionally distilled under reduced pressure. *p*-Methylbenzyl bromide (6.5 g., 69.9%) was collected at 106°/12mm.

Preparation of S-alkyl-isothiourea Picrate.—Finely powdered thiourea (1g.), *p*-methylbenzyl bromide (1 g.) and ethyl alcohol (10 c.c.) were refluxed for one hour. Picric acid (1 g.) was then added, and the mixture heated till a clear solution was obtained. The picrate, separated on cooling, was recrystallised five times from ethyl alcohol, m. p. 203-205°. (Found: N, 17.4. $C_{13}H_{13}O_7N_3S$ requires N, 17.1 per cent).

Similar reactions were carried out with a number of substituted toluenes and the results are summarised in the above table. All the reactions were carried out in dry carbon tetrachloride solution and benzoyl peroxide was added in portions (0.25 g.) twice. No analyses of *S* alkyl-isothiourea picrates, already prepared and reported in literature (cf. Levy and Campbell, *loc. cit.*) have been carried out. In such cases, the melting points of the derivatives are shown within brackets, as reported in literature.

* M. P. s. are uncorrected.

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